

2. *M. separatella* larvae by crop growth stage, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1982.

season (Jun-Oct) (Fig. 1). Regardless of time of planting, rice was prone to infestation at later growth stages

(Fig. 2). Incidence was low Aug-Jan, probably because of even distribution on the research farm and in adjoining local

farmers' fields. However, in Feb-Apr, no farmers' rice crops were in the field and the research farm crops attracted borers. □

Influence of cultivation on survival of the Malayan black bug in ricefields

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Black bugs *Scotinophara coarctata* remain in rice stubble after harvest. If fields are not plowed, the crop ratoons and the bugs continue to feed and reproduce. It is not unusual to find over 100 insects/hill.

We plowed an approximately 1/8-ha portion of a ricefield after harvest using a carabao with moldboard plow, and immediately placed 14 1-m² cages at random in the plowed section and 14 cages in an unplowed section of the same field. Live adults and nymphs of the Malayan black bug in the cages were recorded at 4, 10, 17, 24, and 31 d after plowing.

Significantly fewer black bug adults and nymphs were found inside cages in the plowed field (see figure). Many black bugs were killed outright by the plowing, others died because host plants were destroyed. □

Populations of black bug nymphs and adults in plowed and unplowed ricefields. Palawan, Philippines, 1986.